

Home sweet home? Social mobility and multigenerational coexistence in (southern and western) Europe.

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Abstract

Intergenerational transmission of status is crucial for understanding social mobility and the perpetuation of inequalities across generations. Traditionally, studies have focused on individuals no longer living with their parents, neglecting young adults still in their family home. Given the current emancipation challenges, this demographic group is significant.

This study examines the transmission of socioeconomic status among individuals living with their parents across 15 European Union countries located in the south and west, using the 2020 EU Living Conditions Survey. It innovatively analyses income, occupation, and education simultaneously, specifically targeting older individuals yet to leave the family household. The aim is to understand social mobility mechanisms in this vulnerable group.

Using data from the 2020 European Union Living Conditions Survey (EU-SILC), this study takes an innovative approach by simultaneously analysing income, occupation, and education variables. The main novelty of this analysis is that it has been carried out focusing on older individuals who have not yet left the family household.

The results reveal notable variations in social mobility between different countries, gender, and socioeconomic groups. In general, greater mobility is observed in the educational area, being especially notable regarding mothers. Employment and income-related mobility show diverse patterns, with certain countries exhibiting higher levels of upward or downward mobility.

In conclusion, the study provides a comprehensive and detailed view of how various socioeconomic and demographic factors interact to influence the social mobility of people still living with their parents in some parts of Europe.

KEYWORDS

Social mobility; Intergenerational transmission; EU-SILC; emancipation.

1. INTRODUCTION.

According to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development's report on social mobility (2018), intergenerational transmission of status is one of the main obstacles to equal opportunities in Europe. Although previous studies on social mobility in Europe have been conducted, most have focused on a limited number of countries or have used different methodologies, making it difficult to compare results. Moreover, most, if not all, of these studies, have focused on analysing the intergenerational mobility of children who have become independent from their parents. But what about children who continue to live with their parents? What levels of social mobility do they experience?

In recent years, the issue of young people becoming independent has become a major problem, especially in southern European countries such as Spain, Portugal, and Italy, where the average age of leaving home is getting later and later. Several studies have approached this phenomenon from different perspectives: some authors point to the influence of economic factors, such as precarious employment, lack of job opportunities and low wages (Blanc & Wolff, 2006) or the high cost of housing (Giannelli & Monfardini, 2000) on young people's decision to stay in the parental home. It has also been shown that different housing subsidies from governments as well as various social welfare policies have an influence.

Cultural and sociological aspects must also be taken into account when trying to understand the problem of young Europeans' independence. Studies point to changes in attitudes towards marriage, cohabitation, and family as possible influencing factors in these decisions (South & Lei, 2015).

On the other hand, it is important to note that the intergenerational transmission of socio-economic status has significant implications for society. First, this relationship can perpetuate inequality and social exclusion (Bloome, 2015). If children from low-income families have fewer opportunities to obtain higher education or to access well-paid jobs, they are less likely to break the cycle of poverty and improve their economic situation. In addition, unequal social mobility can also contribute to political polarisation and social unrest (Ares, 2019), to the loss of capital for society (Bauder, 2020), as well as to the wellbeing of society (Dolan & Lordan, 2021), as people would not be using their full potential. Understanding the patterns and factors that influence the intergenerational transmission of status is therefore fundamental to address the social and economic problems facing modern societies. This study will provide new evidence on social mobility in Europe and offer a more comprehensive perspective on a group that has received little attention to date and is likely to constitute one of the vulnerable segments of society, driving them towards lower levels of social mobility.

In this paper, we examine the intergenerational transmission of status for adults (over 25 years) still living with their parents in the 15 southern and western countries of the European Union and in three main areas of study –education, income, and labour-, using data from representative population-based surveys: the EU-SILC. This paper seeks to analyse the existing patterns in terms of social mobility within this group of individuals and therefore it will contribute to the understanding of social mobility in Europe and provide relevant information for the design of public policies to promote equal opportunities (European Commission, 2020).

Unlike previous research on social mobility in the European Union, which has primarily focused on either income mobility or educational mobility or has analysed social mobility as a whole for children living outside the parental home (Bukodi et al., 2019; Prieto-Rodriguez et al., 2010), this study takes a novel approach. For the first time, it comprehensively examines three dimensions simultaneously: income, occupation, and education, and it focuses on a group of individuals who have been overlooked until now. By doing so, the study endeavours to shed light on the mechanisms operating behind the phenomenon of social mobility and the intergenerational transmission of status of individuals who are still living with their parents. This approach contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the complex dynamics of social mobility in the European Union.

This article will be structured as follows: the second section will provide a brief literature review, followed by a description of the data used in section three. The methodology used in this study will be outlined in section four. The results will be analysed in section five, and the conclusions will be presented in section six.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW.

The intergenerational transmission of status has been a topic of interest to researchers around the world for decades. In Europe, the literature on this topic has grown significantly in recent years, partly due to rising inequality (Rochat, 2023) and growing concerns about social mobility.

One of the first major studies on this topic in Europe was conducted by Erikson and Goldthorpe (1992), who examined social mobility in seven European countries and found that intergenerational transmission of status was stronger in southern European countries (such as Spain and Portugal) than in northern European countries (such as Denmark and Norway). Since then, there have been numerous studies examining the intergenerational transmission of status in different European countries.

Breen and Jonsson (2005) examined social mobility in 15 European countries and found that intergenerational transmission of status was higher in Eastern European countries (such as Hungary and Poland) than in Western European countries (such as France and Germany). Furthermore, they found that social mobility had declined in recent years in many European countries.

Another important study in this field is Erola and Moisio (2016), who examined the intergenerational transmission of status in Finland and found that intergenerational transmission of status had declined in recent decades. However, they noted that social mobility remained limited in Finland, especially for people with low educational attainment.

A more recent study by Becker and Schömann (2020) examined the intergenerational transmission of status in Germany and found that intergenerational transmission of status was higher in the Southern and Eastern regions of Germany than in the Northern and Western regions. Furthermore, they found that education was the most important factor in the intergenerational transmission of status in Germany.

In addition to specific studies on European countries, the literature has also addressed the intergenerational transmission of status from a cross-country perspective. For example,

the book edited by Gornick and Jäntti (2013) examines economic inequalities and the middle class in developed countries, including several EU countries. One of the recurring themes in the book is the relationship between education and social mobility, and how educational policies can affect the intergenerational transmission of status.

In terms of reviewing the specific literature on intergenerational transmission of status, Manzoni's (2018) study provides a comprehensive review of the existing literature, identifying the main factors that influence the intergenerational transmission of status, as well as the main mechanisms of transmission. The author concludes that education, occupation, and income are the main factors influencing the intergenerational transmission of status, and that intergenerational transmission of status is strongest at the extremes of the income distribution.

Finally, the study by Pollak (2014) provides a critical review of dynamic models of intergenerational status transmission. The author identifies the main limitations and assumptions of existing models and suggests possible ways to improve the modelling of intergenerational status transmission.

Overall, the review of the literature on intergenerational transmission of status in the EU suggests that education is a key factor for social mobility (Muñoz & Queupil, 2016), and that intergenerational transmission of status remains a major problem in many European countries. Moreover, the literature indicates that social mobility is declining in many countries (OECD, 2018), which may have negative consequences for equality and social justice. The literature also points out that the magnitude of the problem and the mechanisms of transmission may vary across countries and regions (Bezzo & Raitano, 2023), and that research in this field remains necessary to address inequality and promote social justice.

Nevertheless, in spite of the extensive body of existing literature, a notable gap is identified: the predominant tendency has been to examine individuals who have already left the nuclear family, or else the issue has been approached indiscriminately, lumping together those who have achieved independence with those who still reside with their parents, without adequately differentiating between the two contexts in the analysis. This approach omits a crucial dimension of the phenomenon, that of those young adults who continue to live in the parental home. Recognising and unravelling the complexities associated with this group is not only fundamental for a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of status transmission, but also for designing more effective policies to promote equal opportunities and social mobility in all spheres of society. This article fills that gap.

3. DATA.

In this study, longitudinal data from the European Union Survey of Living Conditions (EU-SILC) for the year 2020 have been used for the 15 member countries of the European Union which have the highest percentages of children (over 25 years) living with their parents. As shown in Table 1, the EU countries with the largest figures are the countries of southern and eastern Europe. In absolute terms, Poland, Slovenia, and Spain stand out especially, and in relative terms, Bulgaria, Croatia, and Slovakia.

Table 1. Children not at home vs. Children still at home.

Country	Children not living with parents		Children living with parents		TOTAL
	Number	%	Number	%	
Austria	9.073	95,97%	381	4,03%	9.454
Belgium	10.960	94,41%	649	5,59%	11.609
Bulgaria	11.609	82,50%	2.462	17,50%	14.071
Croatia	12.700	83,80%	2.456	16,20%	15.156
Cyprus	7.267	89,15%	884	10,85%	8.151
Czech Republic	13.497	92,57%	1.083	7,43%	14.580
Denmark	10.169	98,65%	139	1,35%	10.308
Estonia	10.083	91,71%	911	8,29%	10.994
Finland	15.586	97,71%	366	2,29%	15.952
France	16.919	96,49%	615	3,51%	17.534
Germany	18.951	97,23%	539	2,77%	19.490
Greece	24.012	89,08%	2.943	10,92%	26.955
Hungary	10.044	89,26%	1.208	10,74%	11.252
Ireland	7.010	95,44%	335	4,56%	7.345
Italy	31.496	88,43%	4.119	11,57%	35.615
Latvia	9.049	88,14%	1.218	11,86%	10.267
Lithuania	8.041	88,30%	1.065	11,70%	9.106
Luxembourg	4.793	91,75%	431	8,25%	5.224
Netherlands	20.768	97,48%	536	2,52%	21.304
Poland	25.740	85,23%	4.459	14,77%	30.199
Portugal	19.078	87,53%	2.719	12,47%	21.797
Romania	12.247	84,70%	2.212	15,30%	14.459
Slovakia	9.105	83,10%	1.852	16,90%	10.957
Slovenia	15.403	82,73%	3.215	17,27%	18.618
Spain	25.203	87,81%	3.498	12,19%	28.701
Sweden	9.398	98,19%	173	1,81%	9.571
Total	368.201	90,10%	40.468	9,90%	408.669

Source: Own elaboration from EU-SILC data.

Note: Figures in grey highlight countries with the largest percentages.

If we also focus on these countries and observe what happens by age cohort with those individuals who continue to reside in the family home, we can observe that the highest percentage occurs among the youngest individuals, between 25 and 35 years old, which may be explained, on the one hand, by the possible cultural changes mentioned in the previous section, or by situations of job insecurity that prevent the independence of the youngest. Also, it is noteworthy that the next two cohorts, the one corresponding to the interval 36-45 years and that of 46-60 years, also have high percentages of individuals, which can be an alarming fact if the reasons are not only a cultural change (Table 2).

Table 2. Children still living at home (with at least their father by age cohort).¹

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Bulgaria	985	40,01%	766	31,11%	593	24,09%	108	4,39%	10	0,41%
Croatia	1.119	45,56%	613	24,96%	608	24,76%	113	4,60%	3	0,12%
Cyprus	665	75,23%	141	15,95%	65	7,35%	9	1,02%	4	0,45%
Czech Republic	506	46,72%	278	25,67%	224	20,68%	69	6,37%	6	0,55%
Greece	1.410	47,91%	745	25,31%	670	22,77%	102	3,47%	16	0,54%
Hungary	571	47,27%	292	24,17%	280	23,18%	61	5,05%	4	0,33%
Italy	2.115	51,35%	877	21,29%	960	23,31%	151	3,67%	16	0,39%
Latvia	478	39,24%	296	24,30%	383	31,44%	56	4,60%	5	0,41%
Lithuania	449	42,16%	217	20,38%	336	31,55%	59	5,54%	4	0,38%
Poland	2.014	45,17%	1.243	27,88%	945	21,19%	246	5,52%	11	0,25%
Portugal	1.327	48,80%	684	25,16%	575	21,15%	121	4,45%	12	0,44%
Romania	940	42,50%	629	28,44%	536	24,23%	105	4,75%	2	0,09%
Slovakia	901	48,65%	530	28,62%	362	19,55%	56	3,02%	3	0,16%
Slovenia	1.737	54,03%	739	22,99%	632	19,66%	102	3,17%	5	0,16%
Spain	1.749	50,00%	766	21,90%	816	23,33%	152	4,35%	15	0,43%

Source: Own elaboration from EU-SILC data.

¹ Similar data when comparing for mothers for children still living at home.

Therefore, all those individuals who still live with their parents, both fathers and mothers, have been chosen to be able to analyse social mobility with respect to both figures. Also, information on a variety of socio-economic and demographic variables has been taken into account for these individuals and their parents, including age, gender, education level, income level or type of employment (Table 3).

Table 3. Main variables used in the analysis.

Variable	Definition
Age	Age in years
Country of birth	Place of birth of the individual
Gender	Categorical variable: = 1 male; = 2, female
Level of education	Categorical variable: = 1, primary education; = 2, secondary education; = 3, tertiary education.
Level of occupation	Categorical variable: = 0, armed forces; = 1, skills levels one; = 2, skills level two; = 3, skills level three.

Source: Own elaboration from EU-SILC data.

In this study, data on fathers, mothers and children living in the same household have been used to analyse the relationships between educational attainment, wage level and type of occupation between parents and children in the different EU countries mentioned above.

The first variable used in this study is educational attainment, which is defined as the highest level of education completed by each household member. This variable has been categorised into three groups: 1 (primary education), 2 (secondary education) and 3 (tertiary education). The second variable used in this study is the wage level, which refers to the average monthly income of each individual in the household. The third variable used in this study is the type of occupation, which refers to the type of work performed by each household member. This variable has been categorised into four groups: 0 (armed forces), 1 (skills level one), 2 (skills level two), and 3 (skills level three), following the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO).

4. METHODOLOGY.

As said before, data of mother, father and children (over the age of 25 to ensure that they have completed their educational stage) living in the same household is used for the analysis.

The methodology used, are the transition matrices for the calculation of the degree of mobility or transfer of status. The transition matrix methodology is a widely used technique for investigating the degree of intergenerational transmission of status from parent to child. In this approach, a matrix is constructed that reflects the probability that a child belonging to a socio-economic or status category will remain in that same category when he or she becomes a parent. The rows of the matrix represent the category of the parents, while the columns represent the category of the children.

Given a transition matrix P of size $n \times n$, where n is the number of states in the system, the elements p_{ij} of the matrix P represent the transition probability of the state i to state j . This matrix is characterised by the following properties:

1. Non-negative elements: Each entry p_{ij} of the matrix is non negative. In other words, $p_{ij} \geq 0$ for each i, j .
2. Rows that add up to one: The sum of the probabilities in each row is equal to 1. Mathematically, this is expressed as:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n p_{ij} = 1 \text{ for each } i$$

In summary, the transition matrix P looks like this:

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} p_{11} & \cdots & p_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ p_{n1} & \cdots & p_{nn} \end{pmatrix}$$

Where each p_{ij} is the probability of moving from the state i to state j .

A classic study using the transition matrix methodology in the context of intergenerational social mobility is the work of Erikson and Goldthorpe (1992). The authors examine social mobility in several industrialised countries, including Sweden, the United Kingdom, and the United States, using transition matrices to analyse how mobility patterns vary across these nations. Their findings provide a deeper understanding of how differences in social and political structures influence the intergenerational transmission of status.

Another example of research using this methodology is the study by Beller and Hout (2006) in which the authors explore intergenerational social mobility in the United States and compare it with other countries. Transition matrices allow them to accurately measure the likelihood of children inheriting their parents' social status, thus contributing to the understanding of the dynamics of inequality and mobility in different national contexts. These examples highlight the importance and versatility of transition matrix methodology in sociological and economic research on social mobility and intergenerational transmission of status.

5. RESULTS

Next subsections summarize the main results of social mobility in the three areas of analysis: income, education, and occupation, respectively. Main results are presented in form of a mobility index² that takes three possible values: 1 means that the total sample in that country has downward mobility, 2 means that the total sample has no mobility and 3 means that the total sample has upward mobility. Then, some more results on the transition matrices are described with regard to each parent. The details of the transition matrices are shown in the Annexes due to their length.

² This index is presented as a way of condensing the results as there are many transition matrices for 15 countries. It is constructed by taking a weighted average of the proportions of people with each type of mobility. Given that the variable mobility takes three values that indicates the type of mobility, each of them is multiplied by the corresponding proportion of individuals experiencing such type of mobility.

5.1 Income mobility.

Table 4 shows the main results on mobility in income with respect to fathers and mothers. In general, most individuals show zero mobility -especially with respect to mothers-, and a higher percentage of downward mobility when compared to fathers. Then, higher levels of mobility tend to appear with respect to mothers than with respect to fathers.

By countries, Cyprus, Hungary, and Slovakia, are the ones that show the highest levels of mobility, being their index equal to two. On the other hand, we can see that the countries with the lowest index of income mobility are Lithuania and Latvia, with their index equal to 1.50, meaning that most of the individuals on the sample experience downward or null mobility.

Table 4. Income mobility respect to fathers and mothers.

Country	Income mobility Index	
	Respect to fathers	Respect to mothers
Bulgaria	1.74	1.91
Croatia	1.67	1.82
Cyprus	2.00	2.00
Czech Republic	1.59	1.82
Greece	1.66	1.93
Hungary	2.00	2.00
Italy	1.76	2.09
Latvia	1.51	1.90
Lithuania	1.52	1.82
Poland	1.69	1.86
Portugal	1.59	1.79
Romania	1.76	1.90
Slovakia	2.00	2.00
Slovenia	1.86	2.03
Spain	1.69	2.02

Source: own elaboration.

5.1.1 Income mobility respect to fathers.

The tables 1-15 in Annex I show the details of income transition matrices (relative to fathers) for each country and by age cohort.

Overall, there is a trend towards downward mobility as people get older in most countries. However, there are notable differences between nations. For example, in Bulgaria, a high proportion of downward mobility is evident in the older age ranges (61-70 and 70+), with high percentages reaching 65.74% and 90%, respectively. This contrasts with other countries such as Cyprus or Hungary, where downward mobility is non-existent in certain age ranges.

Croatia shows a more equal distribution between the three types of mobility in the younger age ranges, with similar percentages in the 25-35 and 36-45 age groups. However, in the 70+ age group, a more pronounced downward mobility is recorded, reaching 66.67%.

On the other hand, countries such as Italy and Greece exhibit similar patterns in downward mobility, with significantly high percentages in the 61-70 and 70+ ranges. Italy shows more notable upward mobility compared to Greece, especially in the 25-35 and 36-45 groups, perhaps indicating differentiated economic opportunities for younger people in Italy.

Differences in upward mobility are also striking across countries. While some, such as Latvia or Lithuania, have low and consistent shares of upward mobility across all age ranges, others, such as Portugal or Spain, exhibit a higher proportion of upward mobility, especially in the 25-35 age group.

5.1.2 Income mobility respect to mothers.

The tables 1-15 in Annex II show the income transition matrices (relative to mothers) for each of the countries in the sample and by age cohort. Results differ greatly by countries.

For example, in Croatia, there appears to be a considerable proportion of downward mobility in younger age groups. In countries such as Italy and Greece, a significant share of upward mobility is observed in the middle age groups. In contrast to these patterns, nations such as Hungary and Romania appear to show a high percentage of zero mobility across all age groups.

Indeed, compared to the levels of income mobility with respect to fathers, in this case, it can be observed that there are higher levels of mobility with respect to mothers, with the highest proportion of individuals in each age cohort experiencing zero mobility.

5.2 Occupational mobility.

Turning to the occupational domain, the observed pattern on income repeats itself in the work area and higher levels of mobility can be seen for mothers than for fathers (Table 5). It is noteworthy that, in this case, there is greater homogeneity between countries, with all presenting similar levels, whereas in the case of income there was greater variability.

Respect to fathers, the country with the lowest mobility is Latvia (1.67), and the country with the highest mobility, Cyprus (2.00). With respect to mothers, the country with the lowest mobility is Greece (1.96), and the country with the highest, Cyprus (2.24).

Table 5. Labour mobility respect to fathers and mothers.

Country	Occupation mobility Index	
	Respect to fathers	Respect to mothers
Bulgaria	1.84	2.03
Croatia	1.92	2.03
Cyprus	2.00	2.24
Czech Republic	1.78	2.12
Greece	1.92	1.96
Hungary	1.70	2.14
Italy	1.86	2.00
Latvia	1.67	2.09
Lithuania	1.71	2.10
Poland	1.93	2.16
Portugal	1.82	2.15
Romania	1.97	2.04
Slovakia	1.84	2.11
Slovenia	1.95	2.08
Spain	1.83	2.02

Source: own elaboration.

5.2.1 Occupational mobility respect to fathers.

The tables 1-15 in Annex III show the occupational transition matrices (relative to fathers) for each of the countries in the sample and by age cohort.

In these tables it can be seen that Bulgaria shows a pronounced trend towards downward mobility in the upper age ranges (46-60, 61-70 and 70+), with percentages ranging from 47.55% to 80.00%. This contrasts with upward mobility, which is more marked in the younger age groups, particularly in the 25-35 range, with 24.26%.

In Croatia, there is a similar trend towards downward mobility in the older age groups, although with a higher proportion of upward mobility, especially in the 25-35 age group, with 36.01%.

Cyprus presents a more balanced distribution between the types of mobility in the different age groups. Upward mobility stands out in the 25-35 age group, with 33.53%, while in the older age ranges there is a tendency towards downward mobility, although less pronounced than in other countries.

Greece shows similar patterns to Bulgaria in terms of downward mobility in the advanced age groups, although with slightly lower percentages. Upward mobility is more marked in the younger age groups, especially in the 25-35 range, with 33.76%.

Italy exhibits a high proportion of downward mobility in the advanced age groups, similar to Bulgaria and Greece, with percentages ranging from 55.31%

to 75.00%. However, upward mobility is more pronounced compared to the other countries mentioned, especially in the 25-35 age range, with 31.06%.

5.2.2 Occupational mobility respect to mothers.

The tables 1-15 in Annex IV show the occupational transition matrices (relative to mothers) for each of the countries in the sample and by age cohort.

In Croatia, a high proportion of downward mobility in the older age groups (46 - 60 and 70+) stands out. In Spain, a similar situation is observed, with a significant proportion of downward mobility in the 46 - 60 and 70+ age groups.

On the other hand, Hungary shows a relatively high percentage of upward mobility in the 25-35 age group, suggesting opportunities for career advancement in the early stages of professional life.

Looking at Portugal and Greece, there is a relative balance between upward, downward and no mobility in most age groups.

5.3 Educational mobility.

Finally, in the case of mobility in education (Table 6), in addition to seeing that mobility levels are once again higher for mothers, it can also be observed that they are also higher than mobility in employment and income. Furthermore, as in the case of income, there is some variability between countries. In this case the countries with higher mobility are Cyprus (2.19) if we compare respect to fathers, and Greece (2.40) if we compare respect to mothers.

Table 6. Educational mobility respect to fathers and mothers.

Country	Education mobility Index	
	Respect to fathers	Respect to mothers
Bulgaria	1.90	2.13
Croatia	1.93	2.29
Cyprus	2.19	2.39
Czech Republic	1.73	2.15
Greece	2.02	2.40
Hungary	1.64	2.21
Italy	2.00	2.38
Latvia	1.66	2.07
Lithuania	1.71	2.22
Poland	1.98	2.28
Portugal	1.99	2.32
Romania	1.94	2.30
Slovakia	1.84	2.22
Slovenia	2.00	2.27
Spain	1.93	2.28

Source: own elaboration.

5.3.1 Education mobility respect to fathers.

The tables 1-15 in Annex V show the education transition matrices (relative to fathers) for each of the countries in the sample and by age cohort.

In Bulgaria and Croatia, there is a trend towards downward educational mobility as people age. In these countries, older age groups, especially those aged 46-60 and over, show a significant propensity towards a decline in education. On the other hand, younger groups, such as the 25-35 range, have a higher proportion of upward mobility.

In countries such as Greece and Italy, upward mobility is more marked across all age groups, with a particularly strong propensity in the 25-35 age group. However, even in these countries, there remains a trend towards downward mobility in the older age groups.

5.3.2 Education mobility respect to mothers.

The tables 1-15 in Annex VI show the education transition matrices (relative to mothers) for each of the countries in the sample and by age cohort. Again, when compared to mothers, mobility levels are now considerably improved, with many groups of young people being upwardly mobile.

In Bulgaria, a relatively high proportion of upward mobility is evident in the 46-60 and 70+ age groups. Conversely, in Croatia, there is a higher percentage of upward mobility in the same age range, pointing to possible educational opportunities later in life.

On the other hand, countries such as Greece and Romania show a considerable proportion of upward mobility in the 25-35 age groups, suggesting a dynamic of educational upgrading at earlier stages of working life.

5.4 Summary of findings.

Table 7 provides a clearer picture of some of the data mentioned above. Education in the area where countries show the highest mobility (especially with respect to mothers, note the index value of 2.4, the highest in the distribution), while income is the area where countries show the lowest levels of mobility between parents and children. The highest variability between countries is in income mobility with respect to fathers (with a standard deviation equal to 0.16), and the lowest variability is observed in occupational mobility with respect to mothers (standard deviation equal to 0.07).

Table 7. Main index statistics.

	Income mobility		Labour mobility		Educational mobility	
	Fathers	Mothers	Fathers	Mothers	Fathers	Mothers
Minimum	1.51	1.79	1.67	1.96	1.64	2.07
Maximum	2.00	2.09	2.02	2.24	2.19	2.40
Median	1.69	1.91	1.84	2.09	1.93	2.28
Mean	1.74	1.93	1.85	2.08	1.90	2.26
Standard deviation	0.16	0.09	0.10	0.07	0.15	0.10

Source: own elaboration.

To see the differences in mobility levels between countries, the table below presents by type of mobility, the 15 countries in order of highest to lowest mobility in each of the three areas (Table 8 and 9). Several things stand out from this table:

(i) In the case of mobility respect to fathers, talking about the countries with the highest levels of mobility, there is considerable variability, although Cyprus would stand out as the country with the highest mobility on the three areas when compared respect to fathers.

(ii) Continuing with the same Table 8, it can be observed that other Mediterranean countries such as Greece and Italy also have high positions in all three columns. However, variations are observed in the position of countries across the aspects considered, suggesting that parental mobility may differ depending on the area analysed. For example, in the case of Portugal, while it ranks fifth in terms of mobility in education, it falls to the bottom of the list in terms of employment and income.

(iii) In the case of mobility respect to mothers, the education column is headed by Greece, followed by Cyprus and other prominent Mediterranean countries. In terms of employment, Cyprus tops the list, followed by Poland and Portugal. Finally, in income, Italy leads, closely followed by Slovenia and Spain. The data reveal interesting patterns in the mobility of mothers in these countries, showing remarkable variations in the position of each country depending on the aspect considered.

Table 8. Countries from most to least mobile with respect to fathers.

		Education	Occupation	Income
↑	1.	Cyprus	Cyprus	Cyprus
	2.	Greece	Romania	Hungary
	3.	Italy	Slovenia	Slovakia
	4.	Slovenia	Poland	Slovenia
	5.	Portugal	Croatia	Romania
	6.	Poland	Greece	Italy
	7.	Romania	Italy	Bulgaria

8.	Croatia	Slovakia	Spain
9.	Spain	Bulgaria	Poland
10.	Bulgaria	Spain	Croatia
11.	Slovakia	Portugal	Greece
12.	Czechia	Czechia	Portugal
13.	Lithuania	Lithuania	Czechia
14.	Latvia	Hungary	Lithuania
15.	Hungary	Latvia	Latvia

Source: own elaboration.

Table 9. Countries from most to least mobile with respect to mothers.

		Education	Occupation	Income
↑	1.	Greece	Cyprus	Italy
	2.	Cyprus	Poland	Slovenia
	3.	Italy	Portugal	Spain
	4.	Portugal	Hungary	Cyprus
	5.	Romania	Czechia	Hungary
	6.	Croatia	Slovakia	Slovakia
	7.	Spain	Lithuania	Greece
	8.	Poland	Latvia	Bulgaria
	9.	Slovenia	Slovenia	Latvia
	10.	Slovakia	Romania	Romania
↓	11.	Lithuania	Croatia	Poland
	12.	Hungary	Bulgaria	Croatia
	13.	Czechia	Spain	Lithuania
	14.	Bulgaria	Italy	Czechia
	15.	Latvia	Greece	Portugal

Source: own elaboration.

6. CONCLUSION

This research has addressed the question of whether there is intergenerational transmission of status in the 15 southern and western EU countries, focusing on education, wages, and employment, among individuals who still reside with their parents. Through a comparative approach, social mobility was analysed in relation to both fathers and mothers, allowing for a more complete picture of patterns and trends in each country.

The results reveal notable variations in social mobility between different countries, genders and socioeconomic groups. In general, greater mobility is observed in the educational sector, being especially notable among mothers. Employment and income-related mobility show diverse patterns, with certain countries exhibiting higher levels of upward or downward mobility. However, it is important to note that education emerges as the area where the greatest social mobility is observed.

With regard to occupational mobility, in general terms greater mobility can be observed with respect to mothers, experiencing the southern countries lower levels of mobility than the others. In terms of income, lower levels of mobility can be seen, both with respect to fathers and mothers as for example in Latvia and Lithuania, where a large proportion of the individuals analysed belong to a lower income quartile than their fathers.

In addition, it is also necessary to consider variations in social mobility between different age cohorts and how these differ according to the national context. For example, in the area of income mobility, there is a generalised trend across most countries, characterised by a higher concentration of individuals in zero mobility categories - i.e. remaining in the same income quartile as their parents - in younger age cohorts. In contrast, in the older cohorts (46+), predominant levels of downward mobility are identified, which is of significant concern. Within this framework, Latvia deserves a special mention, as, with the exception of individuals over 70 years of age, the other cohorts show a predominant proportion of downwardly mobile individuals, again underlining an alarming situation in terms of income mobility.

With regard to occupational mobility, the findings show parallels with previous observations, with trends in certain countries that are sometimes marginally more unfavourable. Specifically, it is identified that age cohorts aged 36 and older exhibit predominantly downward mobility. This phenomenon implies the presence of individuals working in lower-skilled occupations compared to those held by their parents.

Finally, the educational sphere is distinguished by a remarkable heterogeneity between the different countries analysed. Three predominant patterns of educational mobility can be identified. The first is in line with the trends observed in the income and occupational domains, characterised by stagnant mobility in the early cohorts and a tendency towards downward mobility in the older cohorts. Next, countries such as Latvia and Lithuania exhibit a particularly alarming situation, with a significant proportion of individuals in all age cohorts experiencing downward mobility, suggesting that these individuals are less educated than their parents, even within the youngest cohort aged 25-35. Finally, in countries such as Cyprus, Italy, Greece, Greece, Portugal or Spain, despite not showing high levels of mobility, there is a positive change in the trend within the youngest cohort, with a higher proportion of individuals experiencing upward mobility; however, in this context, downward mobility rates remain a cause for concern.

In conclusion, the results of this research emphasise the persistence of social inequality and limited mobility in most EU countries. However, they also reveal that education plays a significant role in improving opportunities for social mobility. These findings underline the need to implement policies and programmes that promote equal access to quality education and foster social mobility at all levels of society (Andersen, 2019).

Furthermore, it is also necessary to provide the necessary tools and improve policies that facilitate the emancipation of individuals in these countries, since beyond the cultural aspect, there are limitations, both social and economic, that prevent this. This would have benefits both at sociological and well-being levels for individuals (Meijer, 1991; Welzel, 2014; Brieger et al, 2018), as well as for the economies of the countries (Ayllón, 2009), in addition to constituting a fundamental right. The fact that everyone has access to the tools and resources necessary to emancipate themselves, regardless of their socioeconomic origin, which would promote equal opportunities and help reduce social and economic gaps (Sen, 1999). Access to education, employment, and affordable housing are key aspects in this process.

It is also essential to continue researching and refining the methodologies used to assess social mobility, taking into account the possible limitations and biases present in the available data. Only through a comprehensive and continuous approach will it be possible to develop effective strategies to tackle and reduce social inequality in Europe and promote a fairer and more equitable society for future generations.

Finally, as future lines of research that are being explored, three approaches are proposed. First of all, it is necessary to replicate this analysis at a more disaggregated level, considering the different European regions. This will allow for a more detailed examination of the various patterns of existing social mobility, which will result in the ability to design more specific policies for each territory. Secondly, it is important to extend the analysis to a longer period, in order to observe the evolution of the levels of social mobility in recent years and to be able to anticipate its future progression, which will allow earlier measures to be taken. And finally, just as a more exhaustive analysis of mobility by age cohort has been implemented, it would also be very interesting to carry it out by gender, in order to verify the different patterns of social mobility that exist between men and women in this area.

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Ethical Approval

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Competing interests

Not applicable.

Authors' contributions

All authors have contributed to the preparation of this manuscript.

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Annex I. Transition matrices by age cohort for income mobility respect to fathers.

Table 1. Transition matrix of income mobility in Bulgaria.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	185	18.78%	175	22.85%	260	43.84%	71	65.74%	9	90.00%
Null	771	78.27%	570	74.41%	326	54.97%	36	33.33%	1	10.00%
Upward	29	2.94%	21	2.74%	7	1.18%	1	0.93%	0	0.00%
	985		766		593		108		10	

Table 2. Transition matrix of income mobility in Croatia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	421	37.62%	173	28.22%	290	47.70%	78	69.03%	2	66.67%
Null	639	57.10%	380	61.99%	296	48.68%	34	30.09%	1	33.33%
Upward	59	5.27%	60	9.79%	22	3.62%	1	0.88%	0	0.00%
	1119		613		608		113		3	

Table 3. Transition matrix of income mobility in Cyprus.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Null	665	100.00%	141	100.00%	65	100.00%	9	100.00%	4	100.00%
Upward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	665		141		65		9		4	

Table 4. Transition matrix of income mobility in Czech Republic.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	233	46.05%	103	37.05%	126	56.25%	57	82.61%	6	100.00%
Null	238	47.04%	143	51.44%	81	36.16%	12	17.39%	0	0.00%
Upward	35	6.92%	32	11.51%	17	7.59%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	506		278		224		69		6	

Table 5. Transition matrix of income mobility in Greece.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	475	33.69%	238	31.95%	348	51.94%	76	74.51%	12	75.00%
Null	860	60.99%	457	61.34%	296	44.18%	24	23.53%	4	25.00%
Upward	75	5.32%	50	6.71%	26	3.88%	2	1.96%	0	0.00%
	1410		745		670		102		16	

Table 6. Transition matrix of income mobility in Hungary.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Null	571	100.00%	292	100.00%	280	100.00%	61	100.00%	4	100.00%
Upward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	571		292		280		61		4	

Table 7. Transition matrix of income mobility in Italy.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	862	40.76%	305	34.78%	502	52.29%	107	70.86%	14	87.50%
Null	889	42.03%	322	36.72%	293	30.52%	38	25.17%	1	6.25%
Upward	364	17.21%	250	28.51%	165	17.19%	6	3.97%	1	6.25%
	2115		877		960		151		16	

Table 8. Transition matrix of income mobility in Latvia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	243	50.84%	158	53.38%	239	62.40%	49	87.50%	1	20.00%
Null	202	42.26%	116	39.19%	110	28.72%	6	10.71%	4	80.00%
Upward	33	6.90%	22	7.43%	34	8.88%	1	1.79%	0	0.00%
	478		296		383		56		5	

Table 9. Transition matrix of income mobility in Lithuania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	213	47.44%	92	42.40%	198	58.93%	47	79.66%	4	100.00%
Null	210	46.77%	113	52.07%	132	39.29%	11	18.64%	0	0.00%
Upward	26	5.79%	12	5.53%	6	1.79%	1	1.69%	0	0.00%
	449		217		336		59		4	

Table 10. Transition matrix of income mobility in Poland.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	592	29.39%	365	29.36%	426	45.08%	154	62.60%	10	90.91%
Null	1.343	66.68%	826	66.45%	503	53.23%	89	36.18%	1	9.09%
Upward	79	3.92%	52	4.18%	16	1.69%	3	1.22%	0	0.00%
	2014		1243		945		246		11	

Table 11. Transition matrix of income mobility in Portugal.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	630	47.48%	252	36.84%	281	48.87%	98	80.99%	9	75.00%
Null	626	47.17%	370	54.09%	261	45.39%	23	19.01%	3	25.00%
Upward	71	5.35%	62	9.06%	33	5.74%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	1327		684		575		121		12	

Table 12. Transition matrix of income mobility in Romania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	162	17.23%	150	23.85%	190	35.45%	57	54.29%	2	100.00%
Null	766	81.49%	467	74.24%	345	64.37%	48	45.71%	0	0.00%
Upward	12	1.28%	12	1.91%	1	0.19%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	940		629		536		105		2	

Table 13. Transition matrix of income mobility in Slovakia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Null	901	100.00%	530	100.00%	362	100.00%	56	100.00%	3	100.00%
Upward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	901		530		362		56		3	

Table 14. Transition matrix of income mobility in Slovenia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	621	35.75%	193	26.12%	239	37.82%	64	62.75%	4	80.00%
Null	791	45.54%	322	43.57%	274	43.35%	38	37.25%	1	20.00%
Upward	325	18.71%	224	30.31%	119	18.83%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	1737		739		632		102		5	

Table 15. Transition matrix of income mobility in Spain.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	790	45.17%	273	35.64%	430	52.70%	103	67.76%	10	66.67%
Null	733	41.91%	317	41.38%	264	32.35%	39	25.66%	5	33.33%
Upward	226	12.92%	176	22.98%	122	14.95%	10	6.58%	0	0.00%
	1749		766		816		152		15	

Annex II. Transition matrices by age cohort for income mobility respect to mothers.

Table 1. Transition matrix of income mobility in Bulgaria.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	163	14.49%	91	10.41%	74	10.53%	13	11.30%	1	10.00%
Null	935	83.11%	744	85.13%	608	86.49%	98	85.22%	9	90.00%
Upward	27	2.40%	39	4.46%	21	2.99%	4	3.48%	0	0.00%
	1125		874		703		115		10	

Table 2. Transition matrix of income mobility in Croatia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	432	35.15%	129	18.53%	135	18.72%	10	7.69%	0	0.00%
Null	734	59.72%	479	68.82%	530	73.51%	117	90.00%	4	100.00%
Upward	63	5.13%	88	12.64%	56	7.77%	3	2.31%	0	0.00%
	1229		696		721		130		4	

Table 3. Transition matrix of income mobility in Cyprus.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Null	699	100.00%	152	100.00%	73	100.00%	9	100.00%	5	100.00%
Upward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	699		152		73		9		5	

Table 4. Transition matrix of income mobility in Czech Republic.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	244	44.04%	65	20.25%	44	17.05%	3	3.70%	0	0.00%
Null	268	48.38%	202	62.93%	178	68.99%	76	93.83%	6	100.00%
Upward	42	7.58%	54	16.82%	36	13.95%	2	2.47%	0	0.00%
	554		321		258		81		6	

Table 5. Transition matrix of income mobility in Greece.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	309	21.28%	77	9.53%	77	10.27%	15	12.61%	2	11.76%
Null	1.056	72.73%	648	80.20%	591	78.80%	100	84.03%	15	88.24%
Upward	87	5.99%	83	10.27%	82	10.93%	4	3.36%	0	0.00%
	1452		808		750		119		17	

Table 6. Transition matrix of income mobility in Hungary.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Null	636	100.00%	353	100.00%	319	100.00%	73	100.00%	4	100.00%
Upward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	636		353		319		73		4	

Table 7. Transition matrix of income mobility in Italy.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	631	28.59%	108	11.20%	84	8.10%	20	11.49%	1	5.56%
Null	1.155	52.33%	494	51.24%	544	52.46%	119	68.39%	17	94.44%
Upward	421	19.08%	362	37.55%	409	39.44%	35	20.11%	0	0.00%
	2207		964		1037		174		18	

Table 8. Transition matrix of income mobility in Latvia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	189	34.30%	76	20.21%	52	11.53%	5	7.81%	2	50.00%
Null	303	54.99%	255	67.82%	328	72.73%	53	82.81%	2	50.00%
Upward	59	10.71%	45	11.97%	71	15.74%	6	9.38%	0	0.00%
	551		376		451		64		4	

Table 9. Transition matrix of income mobility in Lithuania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	188	36.43%	58	21.09%	60	14.49%	5	7.25%	0	0.00%
Null	295	57.17%	197	71.64%	331	79.95%	58	84.06%	5	100.00%
Upward	33	6.40%	20	7.27%	23	5.56%	6	8.70%	0	0.00%
	516		275		414		69		5	

Table 10. Transition matrix of income mobility in Poland.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	553	24.15%	270	17.81%	157	13.32%	31	10.88%	1	9.09%
Null	1.633	71.31%	1156	76.25%	954	80.92%	247	86.67%	10	90.91%
Upward	104	4.54%	90	5.94%	68	5.77%	3	1.05%	0	0.00%
	2290		1243		945		246		11	

Table 11. Transition matrix of income mobility in Portugal.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	600	41.18%	172	22.16%	111	15.83%	16	11.11%	0	0.00%
Null	780	53.53%	527	67.91%	512	73.04%	118	81.94%	16	100.00%
Upward	77	5.28%	77	9.92%	78	11.13%	10	6.94%	0	0.00%
	1457		776		701		144		16	

Table 12. Transition matrix of income mobility in Romania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	136	13.36%	72	10.11%	65	9.89%	14	11.97%	0	0.00%
Null	871	85.56%	624	87.64%	585	89.04%	102	87.18%	2	100.00%
Upward	11	1.08%	16	2.25%	7	1.07%	1	0.85%	0	0.00%
	1018		712		657		117		2	

Table 13. Transition matrix of income mobility in Slovakia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Null	1.041	100.00%	647	100.00%	456	100.00%	69	100.00%	3	100.00%
Upward	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	1041		647		456		69		3	

Table 14. Transition matrix of income mobility in Slovenia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	607	32.53%	107	12.75%	90	11.46%	15	11.63%	0	0.00%
Null	901	48.29%	434	51.73%	440	56.05%	103	79.84%	7	100.00%
Upward	358	19.19%	298	35.52%	255	32.48%	11	8.53%	0	0.00%

1866

839

785

129

7

Table 15. Transition matrix of income mobility in Spain.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	564	29.98%	123	14.52%	113	12.11%	20	11.76%	1	5.56%
Null	980	52.10%	458	54.07%	539	57.77%	124	72.94%	17	94.44%
Upward	337	17.92%	266	31.40%	281	30.12%	26	15.29%	0	0.00%
	1881		847		933		170		18	

Annex III. Transition matrices by age cohort for occupation mobility respect to fathers.

Table 1. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Bulgaria.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	263	26,70%	221	28,85%	282	47,55%	67	62,04%	8	80,00%
Null	483	49,04%	427	55,74%	240	40,47%	35	32,41%	1	10,00%
Upward	239	24,26%	118	15,40%	71	11,97%	6	5,56%	1	10,00%
	985		766		593		108		10	

Table 2. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Croatia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	271	24,22%	198	32,30%	268	44,08%	77	68,14%	2	66,67%
Null	445	39,77%	287	46,82%	265	43,59%	29	25,66%	1	33,33%
Upward	403	36,01%	128	20,88%	75	12,34%	7	6,19%	0	0,00%

1119

613

608

113

3

Table 3. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Cyprus.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	166	24,96%	42	29,79%	31	47,69%	6	66,67%	2	50,00%
Null	276	41,50%	66	46,81%	25	38,46%	2	22,22%	2	50,00%
Upward	223	33,53%	33	23,40%	9	13,85%	1	11,11%	0	0,00%
	665		141		65		9		4	

Table 4. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Czech Republic.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	135	26,68%	109	39,21%	121	54,02%	58	84,06%	6	100,00%
Null	243	48,02%	133	47,84%	80	35,71%	8	11,59%	0	0,00%
Upward	128	25,30%	36	12,95%	23	10,27%	3	4,35%	0	0,00%
	506		278		224		69		6	

Table 5. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Greece.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	332	23,55%	227	30,47%	316	47,16%	66	64,71%	10	62,50%
Null	602	42,70%	384	51,54%	265	39,55%	31	30,39%	5	31,25%
Upward	476	33,76%	134	17,99%	89	13,28%	5	4,90%	1	6,25%
	1410		745		670		102		16	

Table 6. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Hungary.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	208	36,43%	137	46,92%	170	60,71%	51	83,61%	4	100,00%
Null	232	40,63%	100	34,25%	84	30,00%	9	14,75%	0	0,00%
Upward	131	22,94%	55	18,84%	26	9,29%	1	1,64%	0	0,00%
	571		292		280		61		4	

Table 7. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Italy.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	644	30,45%	335	38,20%	531	55,31%	98	64,90%	12	75,00%
Null	814	38,49%	331	37,74%	286	29,79%	39	25,83%	4	25,00%
Upward	657	31,06%	211	24,06%	143	14,90%	14	9,27%	0	0,00%
	2115		877		960		151		16	

Table 8. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Latvia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	193	40,38%	125	42,23%	237	61,88%	49	87,50%	1	20,00%
Null	176	36,82%	124	41,89%	104	27,15%	4	7,14%	1	20,00%
Upward	109	22,80%	47	15,88%	42	10,97%	3	5,36%	3	60,00%
	478		296		383		56		5	

Table 9. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Lithuania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	170	37,86%	94	43,32%	207	61,61%	47	79,66%	4	100,00%
Null	144	32,07%	93	42,86%	84	25,00%	7	11,86%	0	0,00%
Upward	135	30,07%	30	13,82%	45	13,39%	5	8,47%	0	0,00%
	449		217		336		59		4	

Table 10. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Poland.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	427	21,20%	328	26,39%	406	42,96%	159	64,63%	10	90,91%
Null	934	46,38%	647	52,05%	448	47,41%	72	29,27%	0	0,00%
Upward	653	32,42%	268	21,56%	91	9,63%	15	6,10%	1	9,09%
	2014		1243		945		246		11	

Table 11. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Portugal.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	416	31,35%	279	40,79%	281	48,87%	92	76,03%	10	83,33%
Null	541	40,77%	278	40,64%	213	37,04%	22	18,18%	2	16,67%
Upward	370	27,88%	127	18,57%	81	14,09%	7	5,79%	0	0,00%
	1327		684		575		121		12	

Table 12. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Romania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	156	16,60%	147	23,37%	182	33,96%	52	49,52%	2	100,00%
Null	496	52,77%	371	58,98%	294	54,85%	41	39,05%	0	0,00%
Upward	288	30,64%	12	1,91%	1	0,19%	0	0,00%	0	0,00%
	940		629		536		105		2	

Table 13. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Slovakia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	250	27,75%	194	36,60%	184	50,83%	42	75,00%	1	33,33%
Null	409	45,39%	235	44,34%	146	40,33%	10	17,86%	1	33,33%
Upward	242	26,86%	101	19,06%	32	8,84%	4	7,14%	1	33,33%
	901		530		362		56		3	

Table 14. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Slovenia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	423	24,35%	225	30,45%	249	39,40%	60	58,82%	3	60,00%
Null	768	44,21%	352	47,63%	297	46,99%	32	31,37%	1	20,00%
Upward	546	31,43%	162	21,92%	86	13,61%	10	9,80%	1	20,00%
	1737		739		632		102		5	

Table 15. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Spain.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	527	30,13%	301	39,30%	448	54,90%	95	62,50%	8	53,33%
Null	705	40,31%	315	41,12%	275	33,70%	49	32,24%	4	26,67%
Upward	517	29,56%	150	19,58%	93	11,40%	8	5,26%	3	20,00%
	1749		766		816		152		15	

Annex IV. Transition matrices by age cohort for occupation mobility respect to mothers.

Table 1. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Bulgaria.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	244	21.69%	193	22.08%	173	24.61%	20	17.39%	2	20.00%
Null	570	50.67%	474	54.23%	371	52.77%	58	50.43%	3	30.00%
Upward	311	27.64%	207	23.68%	159	22.62%	37	32.17%	5	50.00%
	1125		874		703		115		10	

Table 2. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Croatia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	265	21.56%	219	31.47%	253	35.09%	75	57.69%	3	75.00%
Null	467	38.00%	285	40.95%	273	37.86%	27	20.77%	1	25.00%
Upward	497	40.44%	192	27.59%	195	27.05%	28	21.54%	0	0.00%
	1229		696		721		130		4	

Table 3. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Cyprus.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	110	15.74%	30	19.74%	22	30.14%	3	33.33%	0	0.00%
Null	286	40.92%	65	42.76%	29	39.73%	4	44.44%	3	60.00%
Upward	303	43.35%	57	37.50%	22	30.14%	2	22.22%	2	40.00%
	699		152		73		9		5	

Table 4. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Czech Republic.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	94	16.97%	64	19.94%	39	15.12%	13	16.05%	1	16.67%
Null	273	49.28%	186	57.94%	148	57.36%	39	48.15%	3	50.00%
Upward	187	33.75%	71	22.12%	71	27.52%	29	35.80%	2	33.33%

554 321 258 81 6

Table 5. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Greece.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	406	27.96%	255	31.56%	234	31.20%	37	31.09%	5	29.41%
Null	578	39.81%	384	47.52%	384	51.20%	55	46.22%	9	52.94%
Upward	468	32.23%	169	20.92%	132	17.60%	27	22.69%	3	17.65%
	1452		808		750		119		17	

Table 6. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Hungary.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	115	18.08%	56	15.86%	72	22.57%	13	17.81%	1	25.00%
Null	291	45.75%	176	49.86%	165	51.72%	42	57.53%	0	0.00%
Upward	230	36.16%	121	34.28%	82	25.71%	18	24.66%	3	75.00%
	636		353		319		73		4	

Table 7. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Italy.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	630	28.55%	288	29.88%	330	31.82%	61	35.06%	7	38.89%
Null	898	40.69%	384	39.83%	424	40.89%	60	34.48%	5	27.78%
Upward	679	30.77%	292	30.29%	283	27.29%	53	30.46%	6	33.33%
	2207		964		1037		174		18	

Table 8. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Latvia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	130	23.59%	64	17.02%	105	23.28%	17	26.56%	1	25.00%
Null	233	42.29%	199	52.93%	224	49.67%	28	43.75%	1	25.00%
Upward	188	34.12%	113	30.05%	122	27.05%	19	29.69%	2	50.00%
	551		376		451		64		4	

Table 9. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Lithuania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	113	21.90%	53	19.27%	89	21.50%	16	23.19%	1	20.00%
Null	229	44.38%	149	54.18%	207	50.00%	26	37.68%	1	20.00%
Upward	174	33.72%	73	26.55%	118	28.50%	27	39.13%	3	60.00%
	516		275		414		69		5	

Table 10. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Poland.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	331	14.45%	219	14.45%	256	21.71%	74	25.96%	6	54.55%
Null	1.033	45.11%	824	54.35%	650	55.13%	149	52.28%	4	36.36%
Upward	926	40.44%	473	31.20%	273	23.16%	62	21.75%	1	9.09%
	2290		1516		1179		285		11	

Table 11. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Portugal.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	262	17.98%	169	21.78%	145	20.68%	33	22.92%	5	31.25%

Null	605	41.52%	380	48.97%	346	49.36%	67	46.53%	6	37.50%
Upward	590	40.49%	227	29.25%	210	29.96%	44	30.56%	5	31.25%
	1457		776		701		144		16	

Table 12. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Romania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	223	21.91%	151	21.21%	130	19.79%	28	23.93%	1	50.00%
Null	512	50.29%	402	56.46%	379	57.69%	56	47.86%	0	0.00%
Upward	283	27.80%	159	22.33%	148	22.53%	33	28.21%	1	50.00%
	1018		712		657		117		2	

Table 13. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Slovakia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	197	18.92%	116	17.93%	100	21.93%	14	20.29%	2	66.67%
Null	483	46.40%	360	55.64%	238	52.19%	35	50.72%	0	0.00%
Upward	361	34.68%	171	26.43%	118	25.88%	20	28.99%	1	33.33%
	1041		647		456		69		3	

Table 14. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Slovenia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	384	20.58%	211	25.15%	239	30.45%	41	31.78%	2	28.57%
Null	772	41.37%	394	46.96%	372	47.39%	54	41.86%	5	71.43%
Upward	710	38.05%	234	27.89%	174	22.17%	34	26.36%	0	0.00%
	1866		839		785		129		7	

Table 15. Transition matrix of occupation mobility in Spain.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	418	22.22%	258	30.46%	360	38.59%	77	45.29%	3	16.67%
Null	730	38.81%	358	42.27%	379	40.62%	61	35.88%	7	38.89%
Upward	733	38.97%	231	27.27%	194	20.79%	32	18.82%	8	44.44%
	1881		847		933		170		18	

Annex V. Transition matrices by age cohort for education mobility respect to fathers.

Table 1. Transition matrix of education mobility in Bulgaria.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	202	20,51%	194	25,33%	273	46,04%	72	66,67%	9	90,00%
Null	524	53,20%	440	57,44%	214	36,09%	21	19,44%	0	0,00%
Upward	259	26,29%	132	17,23%	106	17,88%	15	13,89%	1	10,00%
	985		766		593		108		10	

Table 2. Transition matrix of education mobility in Croatia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	232	20,73%	165	26,92%	277	45,56%	79	69,91%	2	66,67%
Null	532	47,54%	318	51,88%	244	40,13%	27	23,89%	1	33,33%
Upward	355	31,72%	130	21,21%	87	14,31%	7	6,19%	0	0,00%
	1119		613		608		113		3	

Table 3. Transition matrix of education mobility in Cyprus.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	132	19,85%	47	33,33%	27	41,54%	8	88,89%	4	100,00%
Null	219	32,93%	41	29,08%	21	32,31%	0	0,00%	0	0,00%
Upward	314	47,22%	53	37,59%	17	26,15%	1	11,11%	0	0,00%
	665		141		65		9		4	

Table 4. Transition matrix of education mobility in Czech Republic.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	153	30,24%	100	35,97%	124	55,36%	58	84,06%	6	100,00%
Null	253	50,00%	154	55,40%	80	35,71%	10	14,49%	0	0,00%

Upward	100	19,76%	24	8,63%	20	8,93%	1	1,45%	0	0,00%
	506		278		224		69		6	

Table 5. Transition matrix of education mobility in Greece.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	322	22,84%	235	31,54%	334	49,85%	75	73,53%	12	75,00%
Null	464	32,91%	224	30,07%	202	30,15%	22	21,57%	4	25,00%
Upward	624	44,26%	286	38,39%	134	20,00%	5	4,90%	0	0,00%
	1410		745		670		102		16	

Table 6. Transition matrix of education mobility in Hungary.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	221	38,70%	156	53,42%	175	62,50%	52	85,25%	4	100,00%
Null	243	42,56%	101	34,59%	75	26,79%	6	9,84%	0	0,00%
Upward	107	18,74%	35	11,99%	30	10,71%	3	4,92%	0	0,00%
	571		292		280		61		4	

Table 7. Transition matrix of education mobility in Italy.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	499	23,59%	298	33,98%	512	53,33%	107	70,86%	14	87,50%
Null	689	32,58%	280	31,93%	247	25,73%	34	22,52%	2	12,50%
Upward	927	43,83%	299	34,09%	201	20,94%	10	6,62%	0	0,00%
	2115		877		960		151		16	

Table 8. Transition matrix of education mobility in Latvia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	190	39,75%	137	46,28%	239	62,40%	49	87,50%	1	20,00%
Null	190	39,75%	111	37,50%	94	24,54%	4	7,14%	3	60,00%
Upward	98	20,50%	48	16,22%	50	13,05%	3	5,36%	1	20,00%
	478		296		383		56		5	

Table 9. Transition matrix of education mobility in Lithuania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	170	37,86%	98	45,16%	199	59,23%	45	76,27%	4	100,00%
Null	163	36,30%	82	37,79%	86	25,60%	8	13,56%	0	0,00%
Upward	116	25,84%	37	17,05%	51	15,18%	6	10,17%	0	0,00%

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Table 10. Transition matrix of education mobility in Poland.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	412	20,46%	320	25,74%	408	43,17%	161	65,45%	10	90,91%
Null	889	44,14%	583	46,90%	386	40,85%	62	25,20%	0	0,00%
Upward	713	35,40%	340	27,35%	151	15,98%	23	9,35%	1	9,09%
	2014		1243		945		246		11	

Table 11. Transition matrix of education mobility in Portugal.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	346	26,07%	224	32,75%	258	44,87%	98	80,99%	9	75,00%
Null	358	26,98%	258	37,72%	224	38,96%	21	17,36%	3	25,00%
Upward	623	46,95%	202	29,53%	93	16,17%	2	1,65%	0	0,00%
	1327		684		575		121		12	

Table 12. Transition matrix of education mobility in Romania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	179	19,04%	173	27,50%	193	36,01%	55	52,38%	2	100,00%
Null	525	55,85%	334	53,10%	256	47,76%	35	33,33%	0	0,00%
Upward	236	25,11%	122	19,40%	87	16,23%	15	14,29%	0	0,00%
	940		629		536		105		2	

Table 13. Transition matrix of education mobility in Slovakia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	240	26,64%	175	33,02%	180	49,72%	44	78,57%	1	33,33%
Null	450	49,94%	276	52,08%	139	38,40%	8	14,29%	2	66,67%
Upward	211	23,42%	79	14,91%	43	11,88%	4	7,14%	0	0,00%
	901		530		362		56		3	

Table 14. Transition matrix of education mobility in Slovenia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	378	21,76%	204	27,60%	242	38,29%	63	61,76%	3	60,00%
Null	776	44,67%	341	46,14%	284	44,94%	30	29,41%	2	40,00%
Upward	583	33,56%	194	26,25%	106	16,77%	9	8,82%	0	0,00%
	1737		739		632		102		5	

Table 15. Transition matrix of education mobility in Spain.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	484	27,67%	270	35,25%	423	51,84%	103	67,76%	11	73,33%
Null	609	34,82%	268	34,99%	257	31,50%	36	23,68%	4	26,67%
Upward	656	37,51%	228	29,77%	136	16,67%	13	8,55%	0	0,00%
	1749		766		816		152		15	

Annex VI. Transition matrices by age cohort for education mobility respect to mothers.

Table 1. Transition matrix of education mobility in Bulgaria.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	146	12.98%	123	14.07%	104	14.79%	18	15.65%	1	10.00%
Null	693	61.60%	570	65.22%	361	51.35%	47	40.87%	1	10.00%
Upward	286	25.42%	181	20.71%	238	33.85%	50	43.48%	8	80.00%
	1125		874		703		115		10	

Table 2. Transition matrix of education mobility in Croatia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	145	11.80%	90	12.93%	80	11.10%	12	9.23%	0	0.00%
Null	592	48.17%	360	51.72%	302	41.89%	50	38.46%	3	75.00%
Upward	492	40.03%	246	35.34%	339	47.02%	68	52.31%	1	25.00%
	1229		696		721		130		4	

Table 3. Transition matrix of education mobility in Cyprus.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	64	9.16%	16	10.53%	8	10.96%	1	11.11%	0	0.00%
Null	292	41.77%	66	43.42%	31	42.47%	5	55.56%	4	80.00%
Upward	343	49.07%	70	46.05%	34	46.58%	3	33.33%	1	20.00%
	699		152		73		9		5	

Table 4. Transition matrix of education mobility in Czech Republic.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	85	15.34%	35	10.90%	32	12.40%	3	3.70%	0	0.00%
Null	323	58.30%	217	67.60%	143	55.43%	42	51.85%	2	33.33%

Upward	146	26.35%	69	21.50%	83	32.17%	36	44.44%	4	66.67%
	554		321		258		81		6	

Table 5. Transition matrix of education mobility in Greece.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	152	10.47%	65	8.04%	78	10.40%	14	11.76%	2	11.76%
Null	531	36.57%	312	38.61%	352	46.93%	63	52.94%	12	70.59%
Upward	769	52.96%	431	53.34%	320	42.67%	42	35.29%	3	17.65%
	1452		808		750		119		17	

Table 6. Transition matrix of education mobility in Hungary.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	88	13.84%	45	12.75%	34	10.66%	3	4.11%	0	0.00%
Null	357	56.13%	203	57.51%	158	49.53%	32	43.84%	2	50.00%
Upward	191	30.03%	105	29.75%	127	39.81%	38	52.05%	2	50.00%
	636		353		319		73		4	

Table 7. Transition matrix of education mobility in Italy.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	244	11.06%	97	10.06%	91	8.78%	18	10.34%	1	5.56%
Null	842	38.15%	405	42.01%	481	46.38%	72	41.38%	13	72.22%
Upward	1121	50.79%	462	47.93%	465	44.84%	84	48.28%	4	22.22%
	2207		964		1037		174		18	

Table 8. Transition matrix of education mobility in Latvia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	125	22.69%	91	24.20%	82	18.18%	7	10.94%	1	25.00%
Null	285	51.72%	202	53.72%	214	47.45%	24	37.50%	2	50.00%
Upward	141	25.59%	83	22.07%	155	34.37%	33	51.56%	1	25.00%
	551		376		451		64		4	

Table 9. Transition matrix of education mobility in Lithuania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	93	18.02%	41	14.91%	38	9.18%	7	10.14%	1	20.00%
Null	263	50.97%	160	58.18%	195	47.10%	21	30.43%	1	20.00%
Upward	160	31.01%	74	26.91%	181	43.72%	41	59.42%	3	60.00%

516

275

414

69

5

Table 10. Transition matrix of education mobility in Poland.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	246	10.74%	184	12.14%	198	16.79%	64	22.46%	2	18.18%
Null	1.037	45.28%	760	50.13%	528	44.78%	90	31.58%	2	18.18%
Upward	1007	43.97%	572	37.73%	453	38.42%	131	45.96%	7	63.64%
	2290		1516		1179		285		11	

Table 11. Transition matrix of education mobility in Portugal.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	117	8.03%	62	7.99%	63	8.99%	13	9.03%	0	0.00%
Null	565	38.78%	428	55.15%	482	68.76%	96	66.67%	10	62.50%
Upward	775	53.19%	286	36.86%	156	22.25%	35	24.31%	6	37.50%
	1457		776		701		144		16	

Table 12. Transition matrix of education mobility in Romania.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	89	8.74%	58	8.15%	46	7.00%	11	9.40%	0	0.00%
Null	575	56.48%	398	55.90%	324	49.32%	47	40.17%	0	0.00%
Upward	354	34.77%	256	35.96%	287	43.68%	59	50.43%	2	100.00%
	1018		712		657		117		2	

Table 13. Transition matrix of education mobility in Slovakia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	106	10.18%	52	8.04%	44	9.65%	4	5.80%	1	33.33%
Null	606	58.21%	429	66.31%	250	54.82%	30	43.48%	0	0.00%
Upward	329	31.60%	166	25.66%	162	35.53%	35	50.72%	2	66.67%
	1041		647		456		69		3	

Table 14. Transition matrix of education mobility in Slovenia.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 - 70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	257	13.77%	106	12.63%	98	12.48%	19	14.73%	1	14.29%
Null	880	47.16%	382	45.53%	357	45.48%	50	38.76%	1	14.29%
Upward	729	39.07%	351	41.84%	330	42.04%	60	46.51%	5	71.43%

1866 839 785 129 7

Table 15. Transition matrix of education mobility in Spain.

Country	25 - 35		36 - 45		46 - 60		61 -70		70 +	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Downward	237	12.60%	92	10.86%	97	10.40%	24	14.12%	1	5.56%
Null	795	42.26%	441	52.07%	523	56.06%	89	52.35%	13	72.22%
Upward	849	45.14%	314	37.07%	313	33.55%	57	33.53%	4	22.22%
	1881		847		933		170		18	